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Inventory of Beetles of the Family *Apionidae* (Coleoptera) from Australo-Pacific Region (1833-2001)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the family *Apionidae* and their occurrence. The paper includes: 3 subfamilies, 4 tribes, 38 genera, 10 subgenera and 54 species of beetles belonging to the family *Apionidae*.

Keywords: *Apioninae*, *Ixapiini*, *Myrmacielinae*, *Myrmacielini*, *Rhadinocybinae*, *Notapionini*, *Rhadinocybini*

Subfamilies / Tribes

<i>Apioninae</i>241
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<i>Rhadinocybinae</i>241
<i>Notapionini</i>241
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Kingdom *Animalia*

Phylum *Arthropoda*

Class *Hexapoda*

Order *Coleoptera*

Superfamily *Curculionoidea* Latreille, 1802

Family *Apionidae* C.J. Schönherr, 1823

Subfamily *Apioninae* Schoenherr, 1823

Tribe *Ixapiini* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1990

Genus *Papuapion* Korotyaev, 1987

Papuapion sculpturatum (Faust, 1899)

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Subfamily *Myrmacielinae* Zimmerman, 1994

Tribe *Myrmacielini* Zimmerman, 1994

Genus *Myrmacielus* Chevrolat, 1833

Myrmacielus formicarius Pascoe, 1870

Distribution: Australia, New Guinea

Myrmacielus exsertus Pascoe, 1872

Distribution: Australia, New Guinea

Subfamily *Rhadinocybinae* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1992

Tribe *Notapionini* Zimmerman, 1994

Genus *Alissapion* Wanat, 2001

Alissapion zimmermani Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Australia

Allisapion ibaense Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Allonotapion* Wanat, 2001

Allonotapion subulirostre Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Australia

Allonotapion bommelense Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Anapotapion* Wanat, 2001

Anapotapion caledonicum Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia, Loyalty Is.

Genus *Apionocybus* Wanat, 2001

Apionocybus aeneus (Heller, 1901)

Distribution: New Guinea

Apionocybus bennigseni (Wagner, 1912)

Distribution: New Guinea

Apionocybus nigricollis (Heller, 1901)

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Apotapion* Zimmerman, 1943

Apotapion gibbipenne (Fairmaire, 1881)

Distribution: Fiji

Genus *Brachygybus* Wanat, 2001

Subgenus *Brachygybus (Brachygybus)* Wanat, 2001

Brachygybus (Brachygybus) silvaticus Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Subgenus *Brachycybus* (*Notocybus*) Wanat, 2001

Brachycybus (*Notocybus*) *tegminalis* Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Coeliapion* Wanat, 2001

Coeliapion bilocalis Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Coeliapion mednostriatum (Lea, 1926)

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Ganonotapion* Wanat, 2001

Ganonotapion hornabrooki Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Ganoapion* Zimmerman, 1994

Subgenus *Ganoapion* (*Ganoapion*) Zimmerman, 1994

Ganoapion (*Ganoapion*) *clavicornis* (Lea, 1926)

Distribution: Australia

Subgenus *Ganoapion* (*Proganoapion*) Wanat, 2001

Ganoapion (*Proganoapion*) *rhadinocyboides* Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Heterocybus* Wanat, 2001

Heterocybus debilifrons Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Heterocybus oxystomoides Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Ithyocybus* Wanat, 2001

Ithyocybus bilogayensis Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Lissapion* Zimmerman, 1994

Lissapion varistriatum (Lea, 1926)

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Micronotapion* Wanat, 2001

Micronotapion gibbiceps Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Australia

Micronotapion magnicolle Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Myrmacyba* Heller, 1929

Myrmacyba postcallosa Heller, 1929

Distribution: Sulawesi, Moluccas, New Guinea

Genus *Myrmecocybus* Wanat, 2001

Myrmecocybus asekianus Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Myrmecapion* Wanat, 2001

Myrmecapion australicum Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Nanomymyrcyba* Wanat, 1990

Nanomymyrcyba minuta Wanat, 1990

Distribution: Vietnam, Taiwan, Philippines, Sumatra, Sulawesi, New Guinea, Australia

Genus *Notapion* Zimmerman, 1994

Notapion trilobicolle (Lea, 1926)

Distribution: Australia, New Guinea

Notapion riedeli Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Ommatocybus* Wanat, 2001

Ommatocybus simplex Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Platycybus* Wanat, 2001

Platycybus altipetax Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Platycybus missai Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Papua New Guinea

Genus *Schismatapion* Wanat, 2001

Subgenus *Schismatapion* (*Schismatapion*) Wanat, 2001

Schismatapion (*Schismatapion*) *tetahoense* Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Subgenus *Schismatapion* (*Leptotetapion*) Wanat, 2001

Schismatapion (*Leptotetapion*) *magnum* Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Tapinocybus* Wanat, 2001

Tapinocybus sinakiensis Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Titanapion* Wanat, 2001

Titanapion splendidum (Heller, 1901)

Distribution: New Guinea

Tribe *Rhadinocybini* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1992

Genus *Apinogrammus* Wanat, 2001

Apinogrammus sedlaceki Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Diapion* Wanat, 2001

Diapion politum Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Discelapion* Wanat, 2001

Discelapion plumirostre Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Caledonapion* Wanat, 2001

Caledonapion montaguei Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Hellerenius* Wanat, 2001

Hellerenius lobifer Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Himantapion* Wanat, 2001

Himantaion inermipes Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Rhadinocyba* Faust, 1889

Rhadinocyba singularis (Wencker, 1863)

Distribution: New Caledonia

Rhadinocyba sulcifrons Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus ***Megatracheloides*** Lucas, 1920

Megatracheloides chloris Faust, 1889

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus ***Pterapion*** Faust, 1889

Subgenus ***Pterapion (Pterapion)*** Faust, 1889

Pterapion (Pterapion) monstrosum Faust, 1889

Distribution: New Caledonia

Subgenus ***Pterapion (Apterapion)*** Faust, 1889

Pterapion (Apterapion) hamiota (Wanat, 2001)

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus ***Pogonapion*** Wanat, 2001

Pogonapion kuscheli Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus ***Tetrapion*** Wanat, 2001

Subgenus ***Tetrapion (Tetrapion)*** Wanat, 2001

Tetrapion (Tetrapion) krausei (Wanat, 1990)

Distribution: New Caledonia

Subgenus ***Tetrapion (Axinapion)*** Wanat, 2001

Tetrapion (Axinapion) thoracicum Wanat, 2001

Distribution: Loyalty Is.

Genus ***Thyridapion*** Wanat, 2001

Thyridapion araneipes Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

Genus *Zimmius* Wanat, 2001

Zimmius alutaceus Wanat, 2001

Distribution: New Caledonia

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